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ACTION

D 2.15 Workshop Report 2

Coordinator: FVB-IGB
Quality reviewer: CEFRIEL

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D 2.15 Workshop Report 2: Practical Steps to Supporting Best Practice in Citizen Science

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Abstract	This document is a summary of the workshops carried out up to and including the ACTION Accelerator Kick-off Workshop. It describes the topics covered and the outcomes of the workshops.
Keywords	Co-design, Workshops, Participatory Science

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report gives an overview of the execution and outcomes of workshops carried out during the ACTION project up to and including the second round of the ACTION Accelerator. It is intended to be of use to ACTION consortium, researchers and practitioners working with the Accelerator model, and those with an interest in running citizen science projects.

The report details activities since the Round 1 kick-off meeting until the project end. The report includes the outcomes of bespoke co-design workshops with ACTION Case Study citizen science projects, the ACTION Round 2 Kick-Off meeting, Diversity and Inclusion workshops in Round 1 and Round 2, and webinars. It is expected that the structure of the Kick-Off meeting and some of the associated materials will be of use to citizen science practitioners and those conceiving of citizen science projects.

1 INTRODUCTION: The ACTION Accelerator

As part of ACTION's work, we work with on-the-ground citizen science projects that address pollution. We engage with our case study projects, which have been with us from the start, and our pilot projects, who are selected through two open calls, through an Accelerator programme.

Over the course of ACTION we have provided support to a total of 16 citizen science projects from around Europe. Eleven projects were recruited through our [Open Call](#), (due to the pandemic, one was not able to complete the Accelerator) and 6 projects have been with us from the start as [Case Studies](#).

ACTION works with these projects to provide support and expertise through a mentoring programme, which lasts 6 months for all Accelerator projects recruited through the Open Call. We also work together to re-imagine Citizen Science from the bottom up - working closely with ACTION projects to address the most pressing challenges of Citizen Science today.

We work with projects to co-design tools to help overcome hurdles common to citizen science projects, such as data management, creation of surveys, considering diversity and community development. These co-designed tools go on to become part of the ACTION Toolkit, which will remain available to citizen science projects far and wide after the project ends. The timeline of the ACTION Accelerator for Round 2 is shown in Table 1.

A key highlight is the Accelerator Kick-Off Meeting, at the start of the two Accelerator periods. This meeting, held in early 2020 and 2021, gives all ACTION Citizen Science projects the chance to meet, to introduce their projects, to co-design tools and to meet with external experts.

ACTIVITY	Date Start	Date End
Mentor Assignment		11/12/2020
Mentor Training		11/12/2020
First Draft of Project Plan		11/01/2021
Kickoff Meeting	11/01/2021	15/01/2021
Assessment and Support template to IGB		05/02/2021
Revised Project Plan and Budget submitted to KCL		05/02/2021
Accelerator Start		01/03/2021
Impact Assessment Canvas due to T6ECO		10/03/2021
Call with each project for research object mapping	08/03/2021	12/03/2021
Webinar: Creating a Data Management Plan		17/03/2021
Calls for planning Impact Assessment and Data Quality Assessment	20/03/2021	30/03/2001
Impact Assessment Data Gathering (approximate dates)	20/03/2021	18/07/2021
Interim Update Call 1 (90 minutes)		07/04/2021
Motivational Questionnaire Co-Creation Process	18/04/2021	30/04/2021
Motivational Questionnaire Execution	01/05/2021	18/06/2021
Diversity and Inclusion Call 1		14/04/2021
Interim Update Call 2 (90 minutes)		05/05/2021
Mentor Catch-up without projects		05/05/2021
Data Visualisation Webinar		19/05/2021
Interview about Project Lifecycle for Toolkit KCL	20/05/2021	14/06/2021
Interim Update Call 3 (90 minutes)		02/06/2021
Diversity and Inclusion Call 2		16/06/2021
Interim Update Call 4 (90 minutes)		30/06/2021
Sustainability Webinar		07/07/2021
Finalised Impact Assessment from T6ECO		13/08/2021
Final Deliverables Deadline		27/08/2021
Review week	06/09/2021	10/09/2021

Table 1: The ACTION Accelerator Timeline 2021 (Round 2)

2 Bespoke Co-design Workshops

“Our project mentor, Esteban, introduced us to the concept of a formal Data Management Plan and we worked closely with him to write two such plans, one for our environmental data and a second for our microtask data. Esteban encouraged us to publish these DMPs on the Argos platform, which we did (after helping the Argos team identify a bug in their software). This was a fascinating process that opened our eyes to new ways of sharing our data. We generally license our data as Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International, which we chose again for both datasets in this project. But traditionally we have relied on interested parties finding our data through our own platforms and websites; we hadn’t previously considered the possibility of using Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) to share our data more widely and in this more universal way. We are now considering ways to use our datasets as a form of outreach to more specialised audiences.” Restart Data Workbench, Final Report

From the start of ACTION, consortium partners have worked closely to develop materials for use in the ACTION Case Studies. In this second reporting period there have been bespoke co-design workshops aimed at:

- Preparation of the Data Management Plans for all projects
- Consultancy on writing, publicising outcomes and dissemination for WOWNature
- Consultancy on the use of Zenodo for Restart Data Workbench, Open Soil Atlas
- Consultancy on video production: Water Sentinals
- Impact Assessment consultancy for all projects
- Consultancy on designing a questionnaire for citizen scientists that is both simple and scientifically valid for Walk Up Aniene
- Consultancy on navigating financial structures
- Consultancy on further funding for Open Soil Atlas
- Consultancy on engaging policymakers for WOWNature and Open Soil Atlas
- Match-making between current and previous Accelerator projects to facilitate shared learning: Noise Maps and Water Sentinals to share perspectives on how to navigate different stakeholders’ diverse needs
- Match-making with external experts: Open Soil Atlas and the Berlin soil science community
- Match-making between student volunteers: Open Soil Atlas, Restart Data Workbench
- Consultancy on collaborative writing tools
- Consultancy in the context of the Toolkit interviews
- Attendance of in-person events: Open Soil Atlas
- Consultancy on the use of Grafana: Open Soil Atlas
- Data Quality Assessment calls with all projects plus extra consultancy
- Consultancy on Motivation with all projects
- Consultancy on various aspects of data: Walk Up Aniene

3 Kick-off Workshop

“The ACTION accelerator has been a fantastic empowerment tool for both A Sud and Insieme per l’Aniene. The initial workshop as well as the support provided by all experts from the team has increased our capacity to act in the field of citizen science. It provided us with technological and methodological tools fundamental to frame a good quality work in citizen science, tools that we are already using for other citizen science projects we are running. Many contents and links to other resources, as well as the possibility to confront experts on various issues (from designing the questionnaire to data quality to engagement and impact assessment) have provided us much support both for the pilot and for future activities in the field.” Walk Up Aniene, Final Report

For the second Accelerator Kick-off Workshop, the ACTION citizen science projects joined the ACTION consortium online in January 2021. As the meeting was online, the programme was scheduled for 10-14:00 each day, with two evening events. The Agenda for the Kick-off Meeting can be found in Appendix 1. In the second round of the Accelerator, the Kick-off Meeting was scheduled to fall within the negotiations period so that learning from the workshops could be incorporated into the projects’ plans prior to contractual finalisation (see D2.13).

3.1 Workshop design

The meeting design was adapted in light of learning from the first round of the Accelerator, and finalised once the Round 2 Accelerator Pilots had been selected in December 2020. The workshop oriented around a series of participatory sessions that addressed the projects’ needs. The focus for the workshop was to provide inspiration and an overview of important considerations when beginning a citizen science project and the types of support that could be provided by the ACTION team during the Accelerator period. Much of the structure and topics covered in the Kick-off Meeting are echoed in the ACTION Toolkit.

Attention was paid to ensuring sufficient time for orientation of the projects within the ACTION framework and networking including meeting previous projects. As the meeting was online, a number of reference materials were shared in advance including:

- Meeting Agenda (Appendix 1)
- Introduction to the ACTION team plus consortium expertise index
- Introductory videos from the Accelerator projects

Workshop registration was handled through the ACTION Nextcloud Forms app and all materials were provided in a dedicated folder on the ACTION Nextcloud, which is administered by consortium partner UPM. Zoom was chosen as the online platform for the project, taking advantage of the FVB-IGB existing license, and due to stability issues with open source alternatives for calls with large groups. Out of practical considerations, it was possible for teams with multiple members to split attendance for sessions depending on their relevance to the team members’ role within their project.

3.2 Workshop delivery

Following learning from Round 1 of the Accelerator (see for context D2.12, D2.13, D2.14), the kick-off workshop led with a strong introduction to the placement of the Accelerator within the wider

ACTION project, highlighting the links between ACTION research WPs and the Accelerator projects. Project co-ordinator [Elena Simperi](#) welcomed the participants and provided an overview of the ACTION project, followed by a round of introductions from the team echoing the positions shown in the “Meet the Team” slides provided (Appendix 2). A more in-depth look at the consortium’s research was provided, followed by orientation of the aims of the week-long session. Due to unforeseen circumstances, the session on scientific research methods had to be cancelled at short notice, and the rest of the afternoon session was spent with the mentors working closely with their new projects. We reconvened in the evening for a public presentation and discussion with Round 1 project [Noise Maps](#), followed by a facilitated networking event using breakout rooms in Zoom.

The workshop days were split thematically and ordered according to presenters’ availability. After the first day’s introductions, the schedule was:

Day 2: Data. An introduction to the data lifecycle set the stage for discussing Data Management Plans by Esteban Gonzalez Guardia (UPM). Thereafter, Guardia was joined by [Ilaria Baroni](#) (Cefriel) and [Gefion Thuermer](#) (KCL), who discussed topics of GDPR, data collection and data processing to provide an overview of the most crucial aspects of best practice in data collection and management for citizen science. Data Quality was presented as an interactive session by Baroni, using Miro, that aimed at collaboratively mapping the data quality space for the projects. The results of this session are reported in D5.3 and the outcomes of the learning about the projects’ knowledge of data quality issues went on to inform the tools and guidance provided during the Accelerator period. The day closed with a talk on data sharing and publishing by Baroni and Guardia, including an overview of data visualisation possibilities.

Day 3: Stakeholders Mapping and Understanding. The purpose of this day was to provide the projects with information and exercising in considering the stakeholders to their project, including but not limited to their citizen science cohort. The day began with an overview of diversity in citizen science both on and offline by [Kat Austen](#) (IGB) and Thuermer. This was followed with an interactive Stakeholder Mapping and Inclusion workshop led by Austen, which allowed projects to identify and plan to include diverse stakeholders. In the afternoon session a talk on motivation in citizen science was presented by [Neal Reeves](#) (KCL), followed by an interactive session on participation by [Anelli Janssen](#) (DRIFT).

Day 4: Stakeholders Community and Engagement. After mapping and understanding the stakeholders in their projects, the workshop provided support in ideas of how to engage and build communities with the citizen science cohort and beyond. This included a talk on working with communities online by Thuermer, followed by a breakout room session to discuss the implications for individual projects. A talk on Engaging with Policymakers was presented by [Igno Notermans](#) (DRIFT), which also alerted the projects to the ACTION Policy Masterclasses that would occur over subsequent months. After lunch, the projects were introduced to the ACTION Impact Assessment methodology and how this would intersect with their projects by [Antonella Passani](#) (T6ECO). In the evening, there was a networking event followed by a private screening of the documentary film of their work developed by Round 1 project [In My Back Yard](#), followed by a Q&A with the team behind the film.

Day 5: Communication. The final day focussed on the external face of the project, with a communications best practice presentation by T6ECO’s Passani and [Katja Firus](#) who lead dissemination activities for ACTION. This was followed by a Feedback and Discussion session moderated by Kat Austen (IGB).

3.2 Feedback Questionnaire

“I’d say all of [the sessions] were somehow fundamental for the project. All the different variables and aspects of project design are really important and beneficial to the final performance of the project.” Kick-off Meeting Participant

The feedback questionnaire was delivered using [Coney](#), the CONversational suvEY toolkit developed by ACTION partner [Cefriel](#). From 37 attendees, 19 were from the Round 2 pilots. Of these, 9 respondents gave complete feedback via the questionnaire, alongside 3 incomplete responses.

In terms of networking, the majority of participants had watched the videos supplied by the incoming projects in advance of the workshop and found them useful, giving some sense of the ACTION Accelerator community. Participants also reported that they had sufficient networking opportunities during the kick-off meeting, seeing value in exchange of ideas and good practice, being able to discuss experience and challenges. For instance, one participant noted: “Both formal and informal sharing can be extremely useful for the development of the projects. We already found connections between my and another project. Strengthening the relationship within the community and getting to know each other is a very important point, in terms of knowledge sharing, mutual inspiration and community building”. Furthermore, participants who attended the presentations by Round 1 projects reported that these were informative and inspiring. ACTION was reported to feel like an accessible and inclusive community by workshop participants.

The Kick-Off meeting was universally assessed as a positive experience. In answer to the question “How was the Kick-off meeting for you, was it a positive experience?” 7 respondents replied “Yes, a lot!” and 5 replied “I loved it!”.

When asked which aspects will affect planning and implementation of their forthcoming projects, the respondents were split fairly evenly across the different sessions, with the highest number of responses for Data Day (9/10 respondents) and Motivation and Participation (8/10).

Participants were surveyed to assess whether the need, identified in Round 1, that greater orientation was needed for incoming projects with respect to the overall ACTION project. This need was universally met with participants either agreeing or strongly agreeing that they understood how the ACTION Accelerator fits within the project and that their project could contribute to the ACTION research. The respondents felt they knew how to get help from ACTION and that their project’s needs were central to the Accelerator process.

In terms of working with communities and stakeholders, the participants’ interest was spread fairly evenly, with Stakeholder Mapping and Inclusion, Motivation in Citizen Science, Impact Assessment and Communications Best Practice having the highest response rates. Some key highlighted take-aways were reported to be (quotes corrected for grammatical errors):

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- “To question the inclusivity of our pilot, establish detailed map of our stakeholder, start planning engagement and participation, impact assessment canvas, communication planning”
- “Strategies on how to connect and build a better structure in networks”
- “How to engage with CS and incentives. Diversity of online approaches.”
- “The motivation in CS was fascinating (e.g. the different kinds of motivation people have as well as long-term engagement vs short-term engagement)”
- “It pushed me to think from a different angle, to identify biases and try to think of stakeholders I didn't include in my project plan”
- “We used these presentations to help plan our strategies for communication and engagement”
- “Important to be aware of how the diversity of stakeholders included in the project may affect the final result and the success of the project; important to use a set of communication tools to reach different targets when communicating”
- “Ideas about how to increase motivation; understanding about how difficult it is to ensure EDI and to design the project in order for it to be 100% accessible; the importance of studying the impact of the project.”

For Data, the most interesting topic was considered to be GDPR. Some key highlighted take-aways were reported to be (quotes corrected for grammatical errors):

- “Data management plan, management of participant privacy, Epicollect”
- “Importance of accessibility, readability, feed-back loop tools, GDPR, data collection tools”
- “How citizen scientist data is stored/ etc.”
- “The importance of GDPR and how to get licenses while sharing your work with the global community”
- “There are many open source tools to help gather the data; there are many open access public databases where to publish the data; data quality is important but it is also hard to achieve sometimes”
- “Reflections about GDPR; insight about tools and platform to collect and store the data; importance of having a data management plan”

At the end of the kick-off meeting, most projects expected to use all the tools presented during the meeting: Coney, Zenodo, Epicollect and Grafana, with some respondents requesting further training on them.

The respondents were very happy with the workshop, although one respondent missed the possibility to meet in person, which was out of our control, given the circumstances of the ongoing travel and meeting restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic. One respondent suggested that a checklist for planning and administration would have been helpful.

4 Diversity and Inclusion Calls

“We recruited six citizen scientists by reaching out to our community and approaching individuals and organisations we thought might be interested. This targeted approach was suggested to us in the first ACTION inclusion and diversity call, and helped us put together a team that included a broad range of people, some with an established interest in this work (such as a Masters student), others were entirely new to the topic.” Restart Data Workbench, Final Report

Having been introduced during the Kick-Off Meeting, the focus on EDI was maintained through group calls during the Accelerator period. Alongside monthly Interim Update calls, where EDI was discussed alongside other issues, two dedicated Diversity and Inclusion calls were held. During these calls, the projects were facilitated to reflect on their Diversity and Inclusion activities, to discuss how to address challenges, and to share best practice together. Documentation of these calls was made available within the Cohort and Consortium.

It was found throughout the two rounds of the accelerator that collection of certain demographic data from citizen scientists was challenging for some projects, either due to local restrictions or due to the dynamics within the cohort, which pressed for the prioritisation of the citizen science activity over data gathering for monitoring purposes. However, through the Diversity and Inclusion calls, projects were able to report their experiences.

Diversity and Inclusion activities reported in call 1:

- Projects actively reaching out to missing groups
- One project centering their activities exclusively around a neglected demographic
- Using a buddy system to combat digital exclusion
- Becoming active in spaces less traditionally associated with their field of activity
- Ensuring to use the local languages plus multiple translations
- Producing technology guides and creating a role that requires no use of tech to participate
- Using simple technological workflows and ensuring that tools are easy to source
- Engaging with community groups that are already committed to inclusivity
- Asking for feedback on how inclusive the project appears to be
- Running the project as a sociocracy
- Creating instructional materials in simple language and using graphics / icons, assuming limited prior knowledge of the topic in order to bring people in to the project

Diversity and Inclusion activities reported in call 2:

- Observation that it is important to address emerging hierarchical dynamics within the citizen science cohort with targetted activities to increase the voice or confidence of less vocal groups
 - Establishing a safe space for underrepresented groups

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- Challenges to include people without a certain level of educational
 - Creating tasks and activities that are accessible to diverse educational levels
- Physical challenges of accessibility of some research locations for those with limited mobility
 - Creating tasks and activities that do not rely on access to these spaces
- Inclusion of stakeholders other than citizen scientists, who may even undertake polluting activities
 - If focussed on a geographical location:
 - Brokering individual meetings to discuss the research
 - Creating fora in which diverse stakeholders can meet to discuss the location, particularly with the inclusion of local governance so that there is a possibility that action might be taken
 - Interacting with Policy
 - Running events with policymakers and associated stakeholders online to discuss the research and findings
- Reaching out to schools groups and university students
- Sharing research outputs in simple language with well prepared graphics
- Translating materials as a priority
- Creating ambassador positions with the project to bring in communities where there are cultural or language channels
- Creating local offline info-points
- Partnering with local, neighbourhood scale events where diverse community members gather
- Encouraging tool sharing among citizen scientists at offline events

5 Webinars

“These graphs were designed after—and inspired by—attending ACTION’s Data visualisation webinar. The reminder to tell a story with data viz was very timely!” Restart Data Workbench, Final Report

Webinars were presented throughout the second reporting period. Webinar recordings can be accessed via the [Resources section of the ACTION Website](#).

- ACTION Data Portal – June 2020
- Data Visualisation – September 2020

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- Financial Sustainability – November 2020
- Data Management and Data Quality – March 2021
- Data Visualisation - May 2021
- Sustainability – August 2021
- Sociocracy Learning for Citizen Science – November 2021

6 CONCLUSIONS

It is the intention of the ACTION Accelerator workshops to carry out rapid prototyping and co-design in order to develop detailed understanding of ACTION Citizen Science projects' plans and potential outcomes, which inform the work in WPs 4 and 5.

By synthesising sessions on diversity and inclusion, data management, impact assessment, open data, community engagement and sustainability for citizen science projects, these workshops allowed the pilots to achieve a plan for a minimum viable product-version of their projects, and created an environment of exchange where it was clear how their work fed back into and are supported by WPs 4, 5, 6 and 7.

The ongoing support of Case Study projects has resulted in a series of tailored tools that increase the projects' reflectivity, reach and workflows. The tools developed through all the workshops in co-design with the ACTION projects not only benefit the projects themselves but also shape how they will be included in the ACTION Toolkit.

Furthermore, the mode of engagement with the projects and attention to networking has helped to set the foundation of an ACTION alumni network of citizen science practitioners tackling the crucial contemporary topic of pollution.

Appendix 1
Kick-off Meeting Agenda

Accelerator Kick-off Meeting

11th - 15th January 2021

FVB-IGB Berlin

Context

[Please confirm your attendance for sessions online.](#)

This is the link for Monday - Friday 10:00-14:00

<https://zoom.us/j/92573635937>

Password: ACTION

This is the link for Monday + Thursday evening sessions 17:00-19:00

<https://zoom.us/j/92805950496>

Schedule

11th January, Monday

Day 1: Orientation and Scientific Research Methods

Time / CET	Activity	Who
09:50-10:00	Arrivals	
10:00 - 10:20	Welcome / ACTION overview	Elena Simperl (KCL)
10:20 - 10:50	Meet the Team	All Consortium
10:50 - 11:00	Break	
11:00 - 11:45	ACTION: What we do	Elena + Consortium partners
11:45 - 12:00	What is this meeting about?	Kat Austen (IGB)
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch	

13:00 - 13:30	Scientific Research Methods Talk + Q&A	Franz Hölker (IGB)
13:30 - 14:00	Breakout discussion Round 2 Pilots and their Mentors	
14:00 - 17:00	Break	
17:00 -19:00	NOISE MAPS: citizens mapping the changing soundscape of Barcelona's Raval District + Q&A, followed by networking	Marc Aguilar (BitLab)

12th January, Tuesday

Day 2: Data

Time	Activity	Who
10:00 - 10:45	Introduction to the Data Lifecycle including Open Data and the DMP (Talk)	Esteban Gonzalez Guardia (UPM)
10:45 - 11:30	GDPR, Data Collection, Data Processing (Talk)	Gefion Thuermer, Esteban Gonzalez Guardia and Ilaria Baroni (Cefriel)
11:30 - 12:30	Lunch	
12:30 - 13:30	Co-creation Session on Data Quality (Interactive)	Ilaria Baroni
13:30 - 14:00	Data Sharing and Publishing (Talk)	Ilaria and Esteban
14:00	End	

13th January, Wednesday

Day 3: Stakeholders Mapping and Understanding

Time	Activity	Who
10:00 - 10:30	Diversity in CS (Talk)	Kat Austen (IGB) and Gefion Thuermer (KCL)
10:30 - 11:30	Stakeholder Mapping and Inclusion	Kat Austen (IGB)

	(Interactive)	
11:30 - 12:30	Lunch	
12:30 - 13:00	Motivation in Citizen Science (Talk)	Neal Reeves (KCL)
13:00 - 14:00	Participation Workshop (Interactive)	Anneli Janssen (Drift)
14:00	End	

14th January, Thursday

Day 4: Stakeholders Community and Engagement

Time / CET	Activity	Who
10:00 - 11:00	Engaging Communities Online (Talk and Q&A)	Gefion Thuermer (KCL)
11:00 - 11:30	Breakout Rooms Discussions	All Participants
11:30 - 12:00	Engaging with Policymakers	Igno Notermans (Drift)
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch	
13:00 - 14:00	Impact Assessment	Antonella Passani (T6Eco)
14:00 - 17:00	Break	
17:00 -19:00	Networking followed at 18:00 by In My Backyard: Documentary Screening and Q&A	Rio Neiva Associação de Defesa do Ambiente Team TBC

15th January, Friday

Day 3: Communication

Time	Activity	Who
10:00 - 11:00	Communications Best Practice	Antonella Passani (T6ECO)
11:00 - 11:15	Break	
11:15 - 12:00	Feedback / Discussion	All Participants Moderator: Kat Austen (IGB)

12:00	End	
14:00-15:00	ACTION Consortium Meeting	ACTION Consortium

Appendix 2
Meet the Team Slides

ACTION

@ Action4cs

Action4cs

ACTION

The ACTION Team

KCL

Elena Simperl / <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/people/elena-simperl>

As the project co-ordinator of ACTION, I oversee the project and each of the activities and work packages that take place under the ACTION umbrella. I also lead the KCL team and supervise our activities on the open call and socio-technical toolkit. My expertise includes the intersection between AI and crowd computing, including topics such as human computation, social machines, citizen science and crowdsourcing.

Gefion Thuermer / <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/people/gefion-thuermer>

I lead on the ACTION open call and negotiations, and the development of the ACTION toolkit. I will be your main contact leading up to the launch of the accelerator, alongside Kat and your mentor.

My expertise is in online participation and digital inequality, and I am interested in the engagement, the socio-technical aspects of data, HCI and inclusive process design.

KCL (Continued)

Neal Reeves / <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/people/neal-reeves>

I'm a researcher at King's College London and lead on KCL's research and contributions within ACTION in the areas of task design and motivation. My expertise and research focus on understanding and designing for motivation and engagement in crowdsourced initiatives including citizen science, as well as analysing the communication and online communities associated with these platforms.

Eddy Maddalena / <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/people/eddy-maddalena>

I'm a researcher at King's College London, carrying out research on and contributing to the technical infrastructure and socio-technical infrastructure that are key elements of ACTION. My expertise and research focus on crowdsourcing, citizen science and human computation, particularly topics such as quality assurance and engagement.

FVB-IGB

Leibniz Institute for Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries

Kat Austen /
<https://www.igb-berlin.de/en/profile/kat-austen>

I lead the ACTION Accelerator. I specialise in transdisciplinary research and participation and have a particular interest in how art and science can work together to create new knowledge, DIY science approaches to microplastic pollution, soundscapes, environmental justice and EDI (equality, diversity and inclusion). I make research, participatory experiences, music and sound art.

Franz Hölker /
<https://www.igb-berlin.de/en/profile/franz-holker>

Sibylle Schroer /
<https://www.igb-berlin.de/en/profile/sibylle-schroer>

I am coordinator of the “Tatort Streetlight” project, I deal with multiple stakeholders of streetlights, such as authorities of the municipalities, lighting manufacturers, and residents. I focus on the knowledge transfer, interdisciplinary communication and citizen science participation. The aim of my research is to reduce the negative impact of illumination on insect diversity.

T6 Ecosystems

Antonella Passani. I lead the impact assessment activities (WP 7) and I will be your main contact point for these activities. I share this task with the colleagues/friends of DRIFT. We developed an impact assessment methodology that we would like to adapt and apply to your pilots and, of course, take your feedback on board for improving it. I'm a social scientist, interested in participatory practices, (digital) social innovation, social inclusion and interdisciplinary research. I have been involved in many projects supporting the dialogue between ICT, innovation and social and environmental challenges. I'm also involved in the dissemination activities of the project (WP6), together with my colleague Katja and Valeria, our social media manager.

Katja Firus. With Antonella and Valeria I am in charge of the communication and dissemination activities in ACTION. This means that we are taking care of the ACTION social media channels, the website, the organisation of dissemination events as well as the contact to other projects working on and studying citizen science. I am an economist and am leading the sustainability department of T6ECO which has participated in various research projects on e.g. the impact of grassroots initiatives, and the involvement of citizens on air quality control by smart and easy-to-be used sensors.

Valeria Amendola. I'm a content specialist working in advertising and user experience design. Her area of expertise includes user experience, content marketing, and transmedia storytelling. In ACTION I'm part of the T6 team as social media manager. I'll be following your social media and elaborate on your news for the ACTION social media and website.

Cefriel

Irene Celino / <http://iricelino.org/>

Passionate about user engagement, I participate in the ACTION accelerator bringing my experience with gamification, crowdsourcing and human-in-the-loop data gathering and processing. Curious about human behaviour, I investigate the complex interplay between people motivation, sharing and awareness with the scientific world, data science and digital service design.

Ilaria Baroni/ [linkedin.com/in/ilaria-baroni-4620b845](https://www.linkedin.com/in/ilaria-baroni-4620b845)

I am leading the research activities in the ACTION project and I am one of your mentors. My expertise is in data science, user assessment, co-design and human-in-the-loop. I am also interested in research on motivation and engagement, and on the analysis of data quality assurance.

UPM

Oscar Corcho / <https://es.linkedin.com/in/ocorcho>

I “love” Open Data and Open Science, and I can be considered a real activist on this.

That said, I will be happy to help you with any question that you may have on any of these topics (or any other related to Science in general).

Esteban Gonzalez

I am software engineer and I am coordinating the data management activities of the project. I am a passionate of the citizen science and the implementation of the Open Science principles.

UCM

Jaime Zamorano
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Professional astronomer and
Astrophysics professor at Universidad
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Lucía García
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Research assistant at Universidad
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Rafael González
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Telecom Engineer & former DevOps
expert at Telefonica R&D

Currently, support engineer at UCM for CS
initiatives related to ACTION and one of the
mentors of the current ACTION call

DRIFT

Anelli Janssen I work on ACTION's impact assessment, as well as on motivation and participation. I'm also a mentor this round. I research the role of identity in multi-stakeholder collaborations for a more sustainable future. Also, I'm interested in how to make sure knowledge-creation is just.

Igno Notermans I'm putting together ACTION's policy masterclasses. Themes in my work as an advisor and researcher include the energy transition, mobility and alternative structures in economics (circular, sharing, social entrepreneurship & corporate social responsibility).

Katharina Hölscher I'm involved in ACTION's policy masterclasses, by shaping its underlying concepts and the programme. My passion revolves around questions on how societal change towards a sustainable and resilient society can be realised and supported through governance, innovation and research.

DBC

Roy van Grunsven / Dutch Butterfly Conservation

As an ecologist with a special interest in dragonflies I am involved in monitoring of these insects. Monitoring biodiversity would be almost impossible without Citizen Science and numerous citizens contribute to this all around the globe. Within ACTION I am trying to find out to what extent pesticides play a role in the occurrence of dragonflies, naturally together with citizen scientists.

NILU - Norwegian Institute for Air Research

Sonja Grossberndt

<https://www.nilu.com/employee/sonja-grossberndt/>

I am leading the ACTION pilot on students, air pollution and DIY sensing.

I am working on a number of participation and citizen science projects, both in Scandinavia and Europe with focus on air pollution and urban development.

SINTEF AS, Norway

Dumitru Roman

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/titiroman>

...creating value from data. Glad to help you with anything related to data (collection, integration, insights, management, publication, communication, etc.)

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